

Academic Comparison of Skills or Habits with What Students are Taught in Terms of Positive Education and Integration

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Abstract

When referring to an educational philosophy, the word "positive education" refers to one that is all-embracing and embraces a broad range of pedagogical techniques and methods that are developed from several distinct schools of thought. Some of the most important aspects of the approaches and ideas that have been discussed in the preceding paragraphs include proactive problem resolution, the enhancement of student well-being, and the development of great relationships (Halliday et al., 2020). Positive psychology and social and emotional learning (SEL) therapies are two examples of tactics that focus on developing resilience, creating connections, and fostering self-regulation. Both approaches fall under the category of strengths-based strategies (Halliday et al., 2020). In addition, the positive training approach known as positive behavior interventions and supports, or PBIS for short, is something that might be considered a positive training method. PBIS was developed in the 1990s. Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports, also known as PBIS, is a framework that places an emphasis on the promotion of positive child outcomes using proactive strategies (such as behavior-specific praise and positive enforcement of school-wide expectations) that are made available to children. PBIS was developed by the National Center for Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports (NCPBIS). Every single student at the school has access to these preventative methods. These preventative measures are designed to encourage pupils to act in a manner that is consistent with the standards that have been established by the school. One illustration of this may be observed in the way positive youth development programs place an emphasis on the creation of positive developmental environments

and the promotion of well-being among participants in the programs (Cinan et al., 2004). We believe that positive education should also incorporate the use of systems thinking to allow people to work together towards the shared goal of enhancing well-being. This is an expansion on the similarities of positive education that were provided in the earlier instances. As a result of this, we are of the opinion that one of the key aims of positive education ought to involve the application of systems thinking as well as the use of systems thinking as a tool to accomplish this goal. For instance, Kern et al. (2020) recommended the use of positive psychology-informed systems to broaden the scope of positive psychology in light of the dynamics that exist between these components, as well as the interconnectedness of individuals, other people, and the environment. This recommendation was made because positive psychology takes into account the interconnectedness of individuals, other people, and the environment. This proposal is given because positive psychology has to take into consideration the relationships that exist between the aforementioned components in order to be effective. Since positive psychology has to take into account the links that exist between different facets of the field, this choice was taken in light of that reality.

Keywords: *Positive Education, Integration in Education, What Students are Taught, Skills and Habits, Educational Psychology*

1. Introduction

When systems thinking is used, it not only takes into consideration the viewpoints of the people who are a part of the system, but it also considers who is a member of the system, how the system has developed through time, and how the components of the system have evolved. For positive education to be able to contribute to increased equality in educational settings, it is necessary, in addition to taking into consideration the viewpoints of people who are not a part of the system (Kern et al., 2020), to have a certain sort of interconnectivity. We suggest that this interconnectedness be characterized as a lens that considers the kid as a whole, as well as the school and the community.

To go forward with equality in schools, this is a prerequisite for positive education. It is imperative that this be done to prepare the way for a role for positive education to play in the promotion of equality in educational settings. Over the course of the last several decades, policy, research, and

CURRENT SCIENCE

practice agendas have arisen with an emphasis on a constructive educational strategy that is carried out within layered frameworks for the organization and delivery of layered services. These agendas came up as a direct result of the rising awareness of the correlation between good education and better health outcomes. The concept that individuals might be assisted in realizing their full potential via the means of positive education has been the impetus behind the pursuit of these objectives. These agendas have been pushed forward with the intention of improving academic results for students as their major goal, and this aim has been the driving force behind their advancement. It is possible to build more complicated layered frameworks by beginning with the provision of key evidence-based services to all persons. This acts as a platform. In addition, statistics and other support options that allow for the proactive discovery of gaps in projected performance are a key component of layered frameworks. These models are based on the fundamentality of the science of prevention as its guiding principle. In a similar vein, application science has started assisting us in gaining a more profound grasp of the factors that contribute to the effective utilization of these layered frameworks. Because of this, we have a much greater understanding of the components that contribute to the effective utilization of these layered frameworks, which has been of great help to us.

2. Significant Changes in How Challenges are Viewed and Coped with

The body of work that has been done to this point has been essential in promoting substantial shifts in how difficulties are regarded and how they are dealt with. In contrast, the complete integration of a positive educational approach within these frameworks has not yet fulfilled its full potential in terms of enhancing equality in schools. This is because the entire potential of this approach has not yet been realized. It is vital to integrate theory and science with a lens that takes into consideration the complete kid, school, and society to fully achieve the potential of positive education to promote equality. This lens must consider all three of these factors. The use of this lens is necessary to realize the whole potential of positive education. This perspective needs to consider all three factors. This lens is based on theory, and there is a direct connection between theory and the incorporation of a diverse range of working groups in academic research. Moreover, theory is what forms the foundation of this lens. A constructive and enlightening instructional method is presented here.

CURRENT SCIENCE

- (a) *developmental systems theory,*
- (b) *prevention science,*
- (c) *ecological systems theory and*
- (d) *We propose that it promotes equality when it is based on integrated theory and science across applied science.*

will lead to greater equality if it is founded on the theories of ecological systems theory, developmental systems theory, and preventative science. To be more specific, we argue that a developmental systems theory, preventative science, and ecological systems theory are the theoretical foundations upon which a positive educational approach might be built to promote equality. A constructive educational plan should include these three components as its foundational foundations.

They present negative instances to support the assertion that education is one of the most significant social variables that influence human health, and Hahn and Truman (2015) contend that education is one of the most important social factors that determine human health. [Citation needed] This is since men who have completed greater levels of education are more likely to lead healthier lives than men who have completed lower levels of education. Men who have completed higher levels of education are more likely to lead healthier lives. There is a dose-response relationship that exists between the amount of time spent in school and the wide variety of behaviors that are associated with one's health. For instance, those who have completed less than nine years of formal schooling are more likely to engage in risky activities. This serves as an illustration of the dose response that exists between the total amount of time spent in school and a wide variety of behaviors that are relevant to one's health (Hahn & Truman, 2015).

Because we now understand the contributions made in each of the various contexts that influence a child's growth and the connections between each of these contexts, education has been reframed as an intervention for public health. This understanding has allowed us to better understand the connections between each of these contexts. This is since we now know that education may lead to improvements in community health. As a direct consequence of developing this awareness, we now have a more in-depth comprehension of the links that exist across all these different contexts. Within Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological framework, the idea of education as an institution is portrayed as a component of the microsystem. [Citation needed]

It is generally agreed that the kid's microsystem is the system that is most intimately and immediately related with the child. The child's family, the children with whom they interact, their neighborhoods, and the religious organizations that are present in their communities are all important parts of this system. These components, when present in educational contexts, function as vital resources for the growth and well-being of persons, and when individuals have access to them, they help individuals to develop and flourish. "accelerate the development and integration of emotional, cognitive, social and emotional processes" (p. 9), "expand developmental range," "buffer the impacts of stress and trauma," and "promote resilience" are some of the things that Osher et al. (2020) say school settings do.

This means that individuals are incompatible with their normal, healthy growth because of a lack of support and the likelihood of a mismatch in their developmental or cultural trajectory. They pose a threat because to the fact that some elements of the natural world are unavailable to them. This indicates that they are not suitable for the typical, healthy growth of human beings and should be avoided. In addition, prolonged exposure to these maladaptive characteristics in a school environment might result in habituation, which can extend the domino effect of adverse educational results.

In other words, the culture of a company creates an atmosphere in which it is difficult to operate in an equitable manner. Osher et al. (2020) connects the various factors that can have an impact on a child's development and, in doing so, highlights the need to work towards the goal of reducing a child's general susceptibility. This suggests that parents should strive to make their children less vulnerable overall to protect them from potential risks. The creation of favorable circumstances that maximize assets and minimize dangers is ultimately what leads to the development of people as a species, which is helpful for the evolution of humans. However, the existence and danger of a kid's susceptibility may be transformed in the life of a child in a few different ways by schools in a child's life, and the methods that these changes occur vary depending on the child.

3. Shaping a Child's General Sensitivity

Even if it has previously been shown that schools have a significant influence in molding a child's overall sensitivity, it is essential to stress this point once again. In this regard, educational settings are implicated in the ongoing propagation of the unfairness that currently prevails in the world. It

CURRENT SCIENCE

is not appropriate to hold a debate about education as either a benefit or a threat in isolation from interactions with other settings, either in the present or in the past. This is true regardless of whether we are talking about the present or the past. This applies to both the current year and all years in the past. The reflections that emerge because of the cumulative nature of these interactions and processes both inside and between systems are referred to as "developmental stages" and are given this term. These reflections may originate either within a system or between systems. These reflections can be discovered both inside and outside of the system (for example, Masten and Cicchetti, 2010).

In the scenario that was just described, one of the potential outcomes is that the young person would be exposed to an atmosphere at their child's school that might be damaging to them. This not only makes the kid more vulnerable overall but also ensures that injustice will be passed down from generation to generation. As a direct consequence of this, the child's susceptibility in general will likewise rise. One example that is analogous to this is the revision of education policy that resulted in the implementation of more stringent disciplinary sanctions in schools. This reform was enacted to improve educational outcomes; however, it has led to widespread exclusionary disciplinary practices. These practices are not only disproportionate to certain demographic groups (for example, people with disabilities), but they are also disconnected from emerging science about negative childhood experiences. Although the purpose of this reform was to enhance educational achievements, the widespread use of exclusionary disciplinary methods has been a direct result of its implementation. An example of this phenomena is the modification of education policy that, with the intention of enhancing educational achievements, instead results in the widespread implementation of disciplinary policies that include students being excluded from class. This change was made to the law to boost the effectiveness of the educational system as a whole (e.g., Chafouleas et al . , 2021).

Although efforts have been taken to guarantee that the educational environment contributes to assets (i.e., a reduced net vulnerability), it is possible that an ignored focus in the theory that supports what and why has been missed. Recent years have seen an increase in the frequency of these endeavors.

However, doing so may generate issues in understanding the results and, perhaps more crucially, in continuing the program over time. Whether the program is successful, it may be tempting to ask

CURRENT SCIENCE

if the theory matters; however, doing so may cause problems in interpreting the findings. It is normal to ask why theory is essential if the program is successful; yet, doing so may make it more difficult to evaluate the data (Pianta and Walsh , 1998). As an example, we consider the use of disciplinary strategies that include exclusion to be a significant barrier, which encourages us to explore for other options that are more workable. Welsh and Little (2018) undertook an in-depth analysis of the available research on alternate methods for handling disciplinary issues in educational settings. They summed up the whole study group as promising, even though it is still in its infancy; nevertheless, since it is separated from theory, it also has the potential to be troubling. There is a possibility of a mismatch between the theory of action, which supports many alternative approaches, and the drivers of inequality, particularly in terms of the opportunity to use an ecological lens. This possibility arises because the theory of action supports many alternative approaches. The likelihood of this dissonance exists since there is a chance of dissonance between the theory of action that supports many different alternative methods.

Most alternative treatment modalities have apparently concentrated on "insider" child intervention, as shown by the conclusions of their study. For instance, these strategies included activities that aimed to assist the youngster in assimilating into the social standards that were prevalent at the school. This was one of the findings that came to light because of their investigation into the matter. In general, many of the recommended remedies tended to focus their interventions on a specific area, such as teaching students skills, repairing relationships after problematic conduct, addressing prejudices, and teaching cultural sensitivity, or revising cultural sensitivity curriculum. Restoring relationships damaged by problematic conduct, encouraging students to be culturally sensitive, and restoring relationships damaged by problematic behavior were some of the other potential remedies. Although each of these choices appears to have some potential, there is still the possibility that none of them will optimize the long-term beneficial results or the actual implementation of the plan. Even though each of these choices is still a valid option, this possibility exists despite the fact that all of these choices are still available. According to Welsh and Little (2018), discrepancies in the exclusive discipline are inadequately conceptualized in recommended methods to further future study. In addition to this, they suggest working towards an integrated theoretical framework that widens the definition of student problem behavior to incorporate racial and cultural problems in addition to discrimination and prejudice in the intervention. .

4. The Probability of Justice in Educational Settings

The findings of the study indicate that doing so would be an improvement over current practices. Because of this, the definition of problematic conduct would be expanded to cover a greater range of factors that contribute to the behavior. According to Welsh and Little (2018), if you look at this spot, you will be able to identify some proposed next steps for the work that will be done in the future. We totally agree with you and would want to point out that to maximize the potential for justice in educational settings, such an integrated framework should also be connected to the science of child development and education.

Because we are committed to doing all in our power to ensure that educational environments are as fair as they possibly can be, we feel forced to bring this matter to your notice. To create learning settings that are both fair and successful, the notion of school as entities that contribute to the total vulnerability of every kid has to be integrated across a broad range of diverse concepts and academic disciplines of study. This is the foundation that enables fair and productive learning environments to be created. It is imperative that this integration take place to further the concept that schools are a single institution. As the next stage in expanding our position, we will create and polish an integrated framework to promote equality in positive education. This will be done as a move toward expanding our position.

Although a complete children's lens may seem to be a relatively recent development, its roots date back more than half a century to discoveries made by Dr. It all started with a research that was conceived of and carried out by James Comer. This would imply that the lens has been in use for a longer period than the majority of people assume it has been. Comer's school development program (SDP), which takes this approach to education, sees the growth of the child as its primary objective. This goal is positioned as the primary focus of the program. The program includes six distinct developmental routes, all of which are connected to one another and play an important role in the process of maturation of the brain. The use of a method of education that takes into consideration a wide variety of factors makes this objective attainable (Comer et al., 2004). Comer's definition of the developmental route takes into consideration not only the physical, cognitive, psychological, social, and ethical domains, but also the language domain. These domains include physical, cognitive, psychological, social, and ethical development. The

CURRENT SCIENCE

cognitive, psychological, social, and ethical spheres, in addition to the physical and ethical ones, are all taken into consideration.

Through the perspective of developmental systems research, Pianta and Walsh (1998) addressed concerns regarding the utilization of new research on resilience in educational contexts. They stole the concept of a branching tree from Sroufe and Rutter and utilized it in their presentation by doing this, even though they did not have authorization to do so. The metaphor that Sroufe and Rutter (1998) developed also included contributions from Pianta and Walsh's individual views (1984). It is feasible to maintain a watchful check on the processes that, in the end, lead to outcomes if one follows the myriad of different ways in which branching might take place. By following this course of action, one may acquire a comprehension of the factors that contribute to the beginnings of adaptability in the maturation process as well as the paths that it takes. The objective of branches is not to develop in a symmetrical pattern throughout their existence; rather, branches may develop in a variety of patterns depending on the factors that surround their development. Branches can develop in a symmetrical pattern throughout their lives. Nevertheless, development is mostly dependent on being encouraged, and early intervention is offered if branches do not follow the optimal course.

This is of critical significance for the growth and development of a healthy child. This is because the development process is structured in a manner like a tree. The term "developmental relationship" refers to the link that exists between the natural path of human growth and the act of showing concern for the development of others. Actually, it has been acknowledged as the single most essential aspect that plays an active part in the process of building excellent and supportive surroundings throughout treatment, and this factor is connectedness. This realization came about because of the function that connection plays in the process of constructing settings that are positive and helpful. This is since connectedness makes it possible for individuals to speak with one another and exchange knowledge as well as feelings. To making the concept of a developmental connection more operational, Li and Julian (2012) proposed the following definition for it:

"Persistent emotional connection, ever more complex patterns of collaborative activity, and a gradually shifting balance of power from the developed person to the favor of the evolving person" (p. 157).

- (a) In addition, the writers are of the opinion that the effectiveness of the intervention need to be evaluated considering a predetermined list of primary criteria, and that those criteria ought to be founded on the concept of a developmental connection. This indicates that every program, practice, and policy choice must be reviewed to see whether it makes it simpler for people to connect with one another or whether or not it makes it more difficult for people to connect with one another. The following statements were made by Pianta and Walsh (1998) in reference to the topic of applying developmental pathways in the context of a school setting: "In our view, there is a tendency for a singular focus on success stories, whether at the school level or at the individual level. We believe that success develops and that any effort to promote success through repetition is likely ignoring the fact that it will fail" (emphasis added). This is since the tactic has been shown to be successful in a broad range of environments and in a great many distinct circumstances (p. 409). The writers also stress that any attempt at intervention must begin with the understanding that creating outcomes is a process that takes time and includes various impacts that may entail unpredictability. This is another point that is emphasized by the authors. This is since the authors feel that the process of developing outcomes entails the simultaneous occurrence of several effects at the same time. The authors also highlight the need of beginning any effort at intervention with the understanding that it will take some time for outcomes to become apparent. The writers have suggested that this course of action be taken. As we shall see later in the context of the whole community, having strong ties that allow for excellent linkages and interaction between influences is desired for remarkable and healthy development. This will be one of the requirements that we will examine. This is something that we shall investigate in more depth later. The time we spend together will be used to talk about a variety of subjects, some of which are included above. These traits make a substantial contribution to the aspects that contribute to the overall appeal of living in a community. On the other hand, if similar actions are taken out of the framework of link building, there is a greater possibility that they may run across obstacles to continuation.
- (b) One approach to teaching might consist of creating schools that take into consideration the traumatic events that children may have gone through in the past. Another illustration of

CURRENT SCIENCE

this would be the development of social and emotional competence (SEL). These two situations are both instances of potential training methods that may be used at some point. Over the course of the last ten years, there has been a rise in interest in incorporating trauma-based care ideas into school settings. The primary objective of this movement is to ensure that all school personnel are knowledgeable about and understand trauma (Chafouleas et al., 2021). It is essential for them to do their part in supplying a secure and comforting atmosphere to prevent such traumatic experiences from occurring. This motivation originates from the aim to guarantee that every member of staff is aware of trauma and comprehends the significance of their role in delivering it. The developmental linkages are intimately tied with the potential that may be achieved in schools that are trauma-informed; yet this relationship has not always been clearly front and center in the efforts that have been made up to this point. This motivation originates from the aim to guarantee that every member of staff is aware of trauma and comprehends the significance of their role in delivering it. The potential that may be reached in schools that are trauma-informed is intimately tied to the developmental connections that can be made. It is crucial to have the goal of ensuring that all staff members are aware about trauma and that they understand the potential they might reach in schools that include a trauma-informed approach is inextricably tied with developmental connections. The goal of ensuring that all staff members are knowledgeable about trauma and comprehend the significance of their roles is what sparked this interest and continues to motivate it. Recent studies, as well as the vast bulk of the research that is now accessible, include: *developing school environments where staff avoid trauma and responding to trauma or sustaining traumatization* ; and

(c) *trauma effects while paying less attention to their role in providing students with trauma-specific interventions with the goal of reducing their symptomology* .

Both objectives should be prioritized; yet it seems that the great bulk of research efforts are concentrated on (a) (Chafouleas et al., 2016, 2021; Gherardi et al., 2020). Positive education has had a lot of success, but it has not quite lived up to its promise of putting more of an emphasis on the kid. Despite all this success, positive education has not quite delivered on its promise.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The second example is social and emotional learning (SEL), which results in a considerable increase in the amount of work that is placed into restructuring the content that is given to pupils. The overemphasis that was put on academics has been replaced with an emphasis on the skills and routines that are essential to effectively navigate through life. This change in emphasis has allowed for a shift in the focus of the educational system.

This change in emphasis has resulted in a significant increase in the amount of time students spend reconstructing what is taught, which in turn has led to an increase in the total amount of time students spend reorganizing what is taught (for example, self-awareness, perspective-taking, recognizing, and regulating emotions, and relationship skills). Again, the promise of SEL is contingent upon its developmental pathways; yet, for this promise to be achieved, it must be made plain how talents fit into the larger framework of a child's growth and development. Only then can this promise be fulfilled.

Although it is only starting to emerge in study, transformational social and emotional learning (SEL) integrates SEL with significant social identities (such as ethnicity and culture) and an individual's self-image. This is a relatively new idea. This establishes a connection between the individual's self-concept and significant social identities (Chafouleas et al., 2021). The conclusions that may be drawn from the results of a new meta-analysis on motivation across a variety of student outcomes related to academic success, well-being, goal orientation, and perseverance for schools are consistent with trends that have been seen in this field (Howard et al., 2021). The authors contend that schools need to put a greater focus on teaching strategies that foster students' autonomy, are consistent with developmental relationships, and adopt a constructive educational approach. In a nutshell, this signifies that the authors propose that instructional practices in schools should take on a more upbeat and optimistic attitude.

Throughout the whole of the school, the implementation of systems based on tiers is required to achieve this goal. One of the primary reasons for the success in this field of study is largely due to the development of preventive science as a field of attention. Considering that this area of research is one of the primary areas of interest, this is one of the primary reasons for the success in this field of study. Emerging in the late 1990s in fields such as epidemiology, education, human development, and psychopathology, the phrase "the overarching framework of prevention science is a public health model for the conduct, design, and sequencing of research" states that "the

CURRENT SCIENCE

overarching framework of prevention science is a public health model for the sequencing of research" (p. 1, Stormont et al., 2010). Burns (2011) has offered a synopsis of the fundamental ideas behind preventative science, which were first presented by Coie et al (1993). These principles consist of the following:

“addressing developmental processes that could lead to adverse outcomes; addressing predictors of adverse outcomes through intervention before they stabilize; prioritizing intervention for individuals at high risk for adverse outcomes ; and the act of coordinating between various different systems and areas of operation”

Whether they are intense services for a single student, targeted services for a particular group or need, or services for the whole student body, there are many different types of services. There is the possibility of providing aid to the whole student population, as well as providing full services for a single student, targeted services for a particular demographic or need, or assistance for students individually. This is the case regardless of whether services are planned for the whole student population, for a certain segment of kids, or for a particular group of needs. At the level of the systems, data on implementation is gathered to establish whether the initiatives are being carried out in accordance with the plans for each of these initiatives. Identifying performance gaps and allowing population monitoring over time is made possible using universal indicators (such as screening ratings, attendance, referrals, and grades), in conjunction with the frequent examination of collected data. When it comes to catering to the requirements of children, the implementation of MTSS in educational institutions has always meant using a split technique. This is a piece of gear that has not developed throughout the course of time. Actually, the early implementations of MTSS in schools put a major focus on children's academic ability; nevertheless, the program was ultimately broadened to incorporate support with kids' behavioral anxieties in order to meet the needs of the community (Walker et al., 1996; Lane et al., 2016). The realization that there was a lack of support in other areas of student development (for example, social), in addition to the realization that there were difficulties arising from academic and behavioral layered support systems, was the beginning of the transition to comprehensive and integrated layered support systems. This transition began with the realization that there was a lack of support in other areas of student development (for example, social).

CURRENT SCIENCE

These improvements are a reaction to the absence of aid in other areas of student development that was recognized, which led to their implementation (e.g., social). Models such as the complete, integrated, three-tier preventative approach incorporate graded support systems for children's academic work, conduct, and social-emotional well-being. [Citation needed] (Ci3T). A strategy like this one tries to give help to children that is more effective and efficient, and it does so by using tiered support systems (Lane et al., 2016).

to provide evidence of a multi-tiered support system that has the kid, the whole school, and the community all functioning as component parts of the system (Chafouleas , 2019). This is only one of the numerous advantages that come with participating in the program. The following is an analysis of the factors that contributed to the current state of affairs: (Melloy and Murry, 2019; Chafouleas et al., now being published). The proper execution of an integrated strategy for developing tiered support systems is related with the aim of enhancing the administration of justice in educational settings. This objective is associated with the fact that such a strategy has been implemented (Melloy and Murry , 2019). According to the discussion by Chafouleas et al. (inpress), one of the most important aspects of correctly implementing MTSS is collecting data from a wide variety of sources (such as internal student factors, home variables, and classroom management practices) to assist in making effective student-related decisions and supports. In addition, the authors point out that there is little support for decision-making that is based on data. (Chafouleas and others, in the editing of) As a direct consequence of this, we are interested in discovering whether multi-layered support systems (MTSS) do in fact make education more egalitarian for children hailing from a variety of nations.

In the year 1968, Dr. James Comer was the one who is credited with being the first to propose the idea of SDP. The School Improvement Process, sometimes known as SDP for short, is a mechanism for enhancing the level of instruction that students receive at educational institutions. It was conceived with the assistance of concepts drawn from the disciplines of public health, social link theory, and child development. There are occasions when people will simply refer to the School Development Process as SDP (Comer et al., 2004). Because of their focus on altering the whole school, SDP techniques are related to school-based preventative strategies, while HTP philosophy is tied with positive education. Schools are consequently able to operate as a focal point for a broad range of activities, including the promotion of healthy child development, the

CURRENT SCIENCE

involvement of family members in school-based teams and choices, and the maintenance of a continuous professional life. This is since both the concept and tactics of the HDP concentrate on the transformation of schools (Comer et al., 2004). The HTP process is comprised of guiding concepts, methods, and teams, all of which are directed toward the common goal of producing an environment in schools that is conducive to learning for both students and instructors. The HTP method is designed to provide an atmosphere that is receptive to teaching and learning on the part of both students and their instructors. The HTP method attempts to provide an environment that encourages and facilitates educational endeavors on the part of both students and teachers. MTSS is an example of a technique that was developed to assist schools in better managing, organizing, and integrating their educational programs (Comer et al., 2004). The HDP offers a framework that facilitates good communication between many stakeholders to better plan for the future of education and place a greater focus on preventative actions. On the other hand, it is quite probable that satisfying these objectives will not be sufficient, on its own, to guarantee the project's continued success in the long run. Because of this, for the sake of this section, we shall define "whole community" as a combination of an ecological systems framework and applied science to deploy cross-ecosystem strategies that may boost the persistent usage of a positive education strategy. Only this portion of the definition will be applicable to it. This specific definition was selected because it comes the closest to fulfilling the objectives of this paragraph. We have, over the course of this paper, made several oblique references to the significance of cooperation amongst a variety of microsystems in the process of fostering favorable developmental paths. These citations may be found in various places throughout the text. Comer (2020) emphasizes how critical it is for the setting in which any activity involving children is carried out to serve as a compass for directing the activities. This implies that it must be constructed with the participation of all significant players, and it also means that it must be constructed on strengths that are already existing in the context in which it is implemented. Rather of attempting to transplant manual programs into the environment that already exists, it may be more effective to draw from the natural context and use intentional programming to generalize to get better outcomes for both the students and the program execution. Trying to send manual programs is an alternative to this, thus this compares well. This is true not just for part of the student population but for all of the students taken together as a whole (Riley-Tillman and Chafouleas, 2003; Clonan et al., 2004). According

CURRENT SCIENCE

to the Comer Principles of Social Development, interactions between adults and interactions between children and adults are both considered to be helpful relationships. This is true for relationships between adults as well as those between children and adults.

5. Besides Being Mental and Physical Beings

It is also our responsibility to guarantee that our instructors do not encounter such high levels of stress that they are unable to act as loving models for our kids, and we are obligated to take all of the necessary preventative measures to ensure that this does not occur. In addition to having a physical body, each of us also has a mental capability. Furthermore, in addition to our mental and physical selves, we are also emotional beings who maintain relationships with the other people in our life. We are not only the sum of our physical selves or the ideas that go through our heads; rather, we are the combination of the two. If we choose to disregard any of these aspects when we are responsible for the upbringing of children and satisfying the educational requirements of these adolescents and young adults, we are placing ourselves in danger. Programs that focus on the child's overall development, taking into account the child's cognitive, emotional, social, and physical needs, have the highest success rate in improving any aspect of that development. There is a definitive explanation for why this is the case, and it has to do with taking into account the child's needs. The fact that these programs meet the child's requirements in their whole is likely the driving force for their effectiveness.

If you wish to assist children with their academic development, for instance, you will not receive the greatest outcomes if you concentrate entirely on academic accomplishment (even if doing so may seem to be the most effective technique at first look); In addition to meeting children's social, emotional, and physical requirements, nurturing academic accomplishment is the most productive and effective technique for enhancing academic achievement. While this is true, it is also the case that doing so may lead to some of the greatest outcomes. It is said that Donald Hebb is responsible for providing the famous response "A little of both" in response to the issue of whether nature or nurture is more beneficial. The argument that "nature is more important than that" is nonsensical, according to Hebb's answer to the question posed by the speaker. They are intimately connected, and one's growth of both is incredibly vital not just for the development of both, but also for success

CURRENT SCIENCE

in one's academic efforts, professional life, and personal life. They are inextricably linked, and one's development of both is extremely significant (see, for example, Nadeem et al., this topic). In addition to this, we must make it a point to keep our gaze fixed on the objective at all times. The purpose of education is to develop people who are capable of analytical thinking as well as effective communication. There is no longer any space for debate about the identity of the child's parents after the newborn has been delivered. Though the sage is at work, people will say that "they did it," even if the person who really finished the job was intelligent. This is something that people would do, according to Lao Tzu. Lao Tzu believes it's because people are prideful. Self-control may be defined as the degree to which an individual has this amount of authority over themselves (Johnson & Kurtz, 1991: 29, 38–39).

if they are given the opportunity to succeed in activities they identify as being challenging, while at the same time being offered assignments that are within their capabilities, they are more likely to acquire higher levels of self-confidence and greater levels of independence. Children are likely to have a greater sense of mastery as a result of this. For instance, a kindergarten teacher may consider that children of 5 years old are not yet mature enough to exercise self-control or self-control. As a consequence, the teacher may frame events in such a way that children are not required to exercise themselves. Therefore, control does not provide these children with the chance to practice self-regulation, and as a consequence, it does not enable these children to become more skilled at the skill. This is due to the fact that youngsters are not forced to take part in any kind of self-regulation at all, which is the explanation behind this particular phenomenon (Bodrova & Leong, 2007; Diamond, Barnett, Thomas, & Munro, 2007). Because of this, it is clear that both pride and self-confidence make significant contributions to a powerfully positive dynamic (just like The Little Engine That as could). It is unfortunate to say that if we assume we will not be successful, it is also true that we will not be successful very frequently, and the more you think it to happen, the more probable it is to really occur. This is as a result of the fact that we are going to proceed with the assumption that all of our hard work will be for nothing.

The researchers graded each and every student in precisely the same way; the only thing that was different was a line or two that they stated before the test to create the tone and impact student expectations. The students were told that individuals who were similar to them had a tendency to do well on the assignment, while they were also effective in completing the assigned job. On the

other hand, students' performance did not improve when they were informed that other persons who looked similar to them had a higher propensity to do poorly on the examination. It was hoped that providing pupils with this information would inspire them to do better (see, for example, Aronson et al., 1999; Steele & Aronson, 1995).

6. The Amount of Expertise a Teacher Has in the Content Taught in the Classroom

The social worlds of students include the expectations that their professors have for them as an integral component of their social cosmos. The personal objectives that students establish for themselves throughout their academic careers are significantly influenced by the expectations that students' professors have of them as students. At the very least, the level of skill a teacher has in the subject matter that is being covered in the classroom is not nearly as essential as the instructor's expectations for the level of performance the students will display while they are present in the classroom (Rosenthal & Jacobsen, 1968). If the teacher feels that the pupils have what it takes to comprehend the material, then those students will be successful in their academic endeavors (for example, Diamond, Churchland, Cruess, & Kirkham, 1999; Diamond, Kirkham, & Amso, 2002). The majority of the positive psychology programs that have been implemented in schools up to this point have been on a grade-by-grade basis, with relatively brief interventions that have been primarily focused on the content of the curriculum. The purpose of the entire school approach is to incorporate skill development into day-to-day interactions and practices by leveraging collaborative efforts with the engagement of administrators, teachers, and other staff members, in addition to the participation of parents and students. Bringing together the kids and their parents is one way to achieve this goal. This is accomplished by recognizing the whole school community as the unit of change, which guarantees that the approach taken by the entire school will be centered on the process of bringing about change. This is the process through which change is brought about (Jones & Bouffard, 2012; Meyers et al., 2015).

A holistic school approach involves coordinated effort among the following three components, as stated in the Health Promoting Schools Framework (1998) published by the World Health Organization (WHO).

(a) *curriculum, teaching and learning;*

(b) *school ethics and environment; and*

(c) *family and community partnerships.*

When it comes to effectively teaching and learning a curriculum, it is necessary to model social-emotional competencies, instruct skills through the implementation of evidence-based programs, and provide students with continuous and consistent opportunities to practice these skills throughout the course of normal classroom conditions. In order for students to effectively learn and teach a curriculum, it is also necessary to provide them with examples of social and emotional competency (Oberle et al., 2016).

7. Conclusion

At the level of the school, skills are enhanced extra-curriculously via policies aimed to foster a healthy school environment, all staff training, organizational structure, and day-to-day activities in the school, all of which assist young people grow in all areas. This is done so that students may realize their full potential in each of these facets of their education. This is done so that students have the greatest possible possibility of reaching their full potential in each of these facets of their education. This is done so that students may attain their maximum potential. To put it another way, it is beneficial for children's growth in each of these areas to have a supportive environment in the classroom where they are learning (Jones & Bouffard , 2012; Meyers et al ., 2015). Learning is not confined to the confines of the school environment; rather, with the application of the "whole school approach," it is ensured that the student takes place not only in the environment of the school, but also in the environment of the home. Learning is not limited to the boundaries of the school environment. In addition, the academic achievement of pupils attending these schools is given the same amount of priority as that accorded to the many other components of the educational program (Hoare et al ., 2017; White & Waters , 2015). Positive education has been implemented in all three schools, and as a direct consequence of that implementation, there has been a discernible increase in the overall quality of the settings inside the schools. This is due to the fact that positive education is employed as a methodology across the whole of the institution (World Government Summit & IPEN, 2017). The use of the positive education model as a means of fostering growth by means of the practice, instruction, and instillation of the concepts of positive psychology is the core focus of this model. This methodology also employs the positive education

model in order to foster growth by using the positive education paradigm (Norrish et al., 2013). In order to accomplish this goal during the OEP, the discourse should center mostly on the fundamental ideas and ideals that are held in common by all of the members of the team. After the students have collaborated in small groups to determine their own basic beliefs as well as those that are shared by their peers, they will develop a set of guiding principles for their lives, with each set consisting of around five principles. Students may benefit from an educational setting in which there is a large presence of similar values among all participants. This kind of setting may be advantageous (MacNeil et al., 2009). Teachers at thirteen schools in the Netherlands that are now using the PEP technique are able to foster talks on a broad variety of moral and ethical subjects with the assistance of personal life rules developed by the students themselves (eg respect, safety, courtesy, humor). The education that young people get in these fundamentals of life is influenced by a variety of factors, including the curriculum, the environment of the real schoolyard, the contacts that the children have with their families, and the dynamics that occur within the group. It is feasible to increase 'well-being' and 'commitment' process indicators by integrating activities in the curriculum and school culture that are closely related with the views and ideals of the teaching staff. This is one way that this improvement may be accomplished.

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